

DIELECTROMETRY AS A CURE MONITORING TECHNIQUE FOR COMPOSITE/RESIN PROCESSING

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Brief background of composite development and the need for cure monitoring is discussed. Three forms of cure monitoring by dielectric analysis are explained. Emphasis on dielectrometry. Examples of data are shown and analysis given. Epoxy and non-epoxy systems. Limitations of dielectrometry mentioned.

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INTRODUCTION

Seventy-three years ago two brothers from my home town visited Paris in an effort to persuade the French government to buy their airplane. Wilbur and Orville Wright may have been more interested in cotton cloth and spruce lumber than in aluminum alloys and graphite/epoxy composites, but their desire to extend the knowledge and capability of flight certainly coincides with our goals, here, today.

The earliest, most significant, man-made composites utilized fiber glass; but its low modulus values contributed to its being replaced with graphite fiber, and for perhaps the past ten or more years graphite fibers embedded into an epoxy matrix have been referred to as "advanced composites". The major problem areas of "will the fiber stick to the matrix?" and the plasticizing influence of moisture have been largely better understood and to a workable degree overcome. The problem of high cost has also been, at least partially, depleted with greater volume usage; but a problem that remains, somewhat comparable to the melting and casting of a metallic alloy, is that of processing the composite. A combination of time and temperature must be utilized to convert the tacky, somewhat oligomerized pre-preg into an integral, polymerized composite.

Such techniques as differential scanning calorimetry, liquid and GP chromatography, infrared spectroscopy, atomic absorption, and elemental analysis provide excellent laboratory tools for resin analysis or quality control, but cannot be adapted to continuous monitoring duty as the pre-preg cures. Electronic analysis was developed for just this purpose.

There are essentially three forms of electronic analysis: Ionographing, Phaseometry, and Dielectrometry.

IONOGRAPHING

This is the simplest and least expensive technique. A macro-schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 1. A DC signal is sent through the resin in series with a variable resistor. The voltage across the reference resistor is monitored as the resin is given its cure cycle. Voltages changes are plotted as a function of time in the run.

This is the least definitive of the electronic techniques and not a great deal of work has been done with it. The changes that are seen in the voltage are minimal in number and correlation with resin behavior and the other two techniques is not always good. Some work that has been done in this area has been under United States Air Force sponsorship to Lockheed Aircraft. [1]

PHASEOMETRY

The method of Phaseometry may at first appear similar to Ionographing in that a signal is sent through a reference resistor and the resin in series. However, the signal is taken from an AC oscillator and a phasemeter is placed across the resistor, Fig. 2. The phase angle and voltage drop are obtained as a function of time in the run. These parameters are taken across the reference resistor and then related to activities within the resin.

Considerably more information is available here than with Ionographing and the electronics can be such that the signal/noise ratio remains high and a wide test range is available. The assembly can be designed with off-the-shelf components or, as in the case herein, packaged with the dielectric unit.

DIELECTROMETRY

This technique is the most used of the three. The resin (pre-preg can be used as well) in this case is made the dielectric in a parallel plate capacitor and capacitance and dissipation values are monitored as a function of time in the run. Fig. 3 shows the lay-ups we have used for both dielectrometry and phaseometry. Note that there may be inert insulating film between the electrodes in the capacitor but resin-to-metal contact is necessary in phaseometric studies.

Shielding plates are also useful placed above and below the resin containment. The entire assembly is placed between the platens of a small press where heat is applied via the prescribed cycle. The press also serves to maintain a fixed separation of the electrode plates.

The dielectric method provides a measure of dipole activity. An increase in capacitance, for example, indicates more, or greater, dipoles being established. As the cell polarity changes the dipoles attempt to rotate with the field to maintain alignment. To the extent that they cannot do this a rise in dissipation results. For processing or studying polymeric materials dissipation changes are generally more revealing. Factors that influence dissipation include softening, solvent or moisture release, and such chemical activity as advancement (i.e., partial polymerization) and cure (full polymerization).

These phenomena are evident on the following figures concerning specific resin systems.

3501

Fig. 4 shows the dielectric trace for 3501-5A resin, an epoxy based formulation from Hercules.

This is perhaps the most studied resin of all from a dielectric standpoint. The first dissipation peak is interpreted as due to softening and flow of the resin. There is no corresponding ΔH peak on the DSC curve and thus no heat involved. Between the two dissipation peaks, the material is in a liquid state of minimum viscosity. Dipole rotation is quite easy here and the capacitance grows apace. With the temperature approaching 177°C the resin formulation begins to polymerize and these chemical changes dominate the dielectric properties.

One of the keys in successful composite processing is to apply the consolidating pressure at the proper time. Normally, this is done solely as a function of temperature, but the dissipation signal is a constant monitor that can be seen and, unlike temperature, is reflective of the part and not the autoclave. Work has shown that for this system (3501) the optimum point of pressure application is on the upward sweep of the second peak in the dissipation curve whenever it occurs,

and it can occur at somewhat different temperatures depending on the history of the pre-preg. This then, is the practical value of dielectrometry, that the autoclave operator can "see" the part constantly during cure and make processing decisions accordingly.

But from a research standpoint, dielectrometry also has its value. Moisture effects and resin advancement studies for instance have been reported elsewhere [2,3]. The effects of frequency also add a parameter and Fig. 5 shows these effects with this resin system.

A similar overall trace is recorded as before only now the vertical variations of capacitance and dissipation are seen as a continuing function of frequency. The frequency was varied 0.1 kHz - 1.0 kHz at a rate of nearly two minutes to cover the complete range up and back. An oddity that can be noted here is in the dissipation curve. Initially, the maximum dissipation signal comes from the minimum frequency (0.1 kHz). However, from the apex of the first peak to that of the second, the maximum dissipation signal occurs at maximum frequency (1.0 kHz). A much lower dissipation sensitivity to frequency is also noted during the peak to peak region of minimum viscosity. Viscosities, by the way, correlate very well with dissipation, falling rapidly during the first peak and rising just as rapidly at the onset of the second dissipation peak.

5208

Another resin (or again, pre-preg) system that has been studied dielectrically is Narmco's 5208. It is also epoxy based and its cure cycle and dielectric signals are shown on Fig. 6.

Note that the cure for this system requires a thermal dwell midway through the cycle. The dissipation regions are indicated as to their most probable relations with the resin. Processing pressure is applied at the end of the thermal dwell or, dielectrically, following the advancement region.

As with 3501 a "switch" in the dissipation signal is noted with this system when the frequency is varied as seen in Fig. 7. Further work is necessary to elucidate the reasons and mechanisms governing this changing dissipation/frequency response.

OTHER EPOXY-BASED RESINS

Several other epoxy-based systems have been studied such as 934 and 5505 (designed for boron fiber) and these results are shown in Figs. 8 and 9. By and large, the results are similar. Dissipation peaks are observed during regions of flow, advancement and cure.

NON-EPOXY BASED SYSTEMS

Some more limited dielectric studies are progressing on resin formulations designed for higher temperature service. These are generally more ring-like in nature and are still in the non-formulary stage; i.e., only the base resin is available. An example of this class are the polyimides, Fig. 10.

Here the "R" groups may be aromatic or aliphatic and a wide variety of substituents have been used. The difficulty in monitoring these type materials is the high temperature requirement. Commercial equipment is usually limited to about 300°C and this is just into the polymeric reaction range for many of them. Additive and cure initiator studies are underway.

LIMITATIONS OF DIELECTROMETRY

In part dielectrometry is controlled by the equation for capacitance,

$$c = \frac{\epsilon(T) A}{d} \quad (1)$$

where c = capacitance,
 $\epsilon(T)$ = dielectric constant as a function of temperature,
 A = area of cell,
 d = distance of plate separation.

For a given resin material the "A" and "d" terms become limiting and the electronic signal quickly shows distortion as the plate separation increases. For an approximately 5.08cm x 5.08cm (2"x2") cell the signals as shown on Figs. 4-8 become severely distorted with a plate separation of approximately two millimeters. This amounts to some 25-30 plies of pre-preg. Compensation can be gained by increasing the cell area but work is not yet sufficiently along to set limits. The range of capacitance measurement, for commonly available equipment, is up to 500PF. Cell areas in the vicinity of 30.48cmx30.48cm (12"x12") will quickly

exceed this figure at a separation of around 2-2.5mm with an epoxy-based resin. Again, more work is needed for better correlation and balance between the "A" and "d" ranges for optimum cure monitoring.

However, the main problem of successfully cure monitoring thick parts is not one of electronically balancing the detection equipment. Rather, the thick part, and over 100 plies is not uncommon, creates gradients from the outer surface to the center. Primarily due to thermal differences, these gradients are evident in chemistry (i.e., a chemical or "cure" gradient) and viscosity. Further compounding the processing problem is the release of moisture or solvent or entrapped gases striving to be released against the thermal gradient. The use of metal tooling can also be a factor as it may work as a heat sink.

For any or all of these reasons cure cycles for thick composite parts employ more thermal dwells in an attempt to minimize the gradient effect and equilibrate temperatures. Dielectrometry can do no more than record the average of the specific electronic property across the resin as an instantaneous function of time and temperature.

REFERENCES

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